

A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOCATION – BASED SERVICES IN RETAIL MARKETING

Dr.S. Vijayalakshmi

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce,
Sindhi College, Chennai-600077, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of location-based services (LBS) in retail marketing, focusing on how these tools enhance customer engagement and targeting precision. LBS leverage mobile devices, positioning systems, and communication networks to deliver location-specific information to users, significantly impacting mobile commerce. The research highlights how LBS facilitate personalized promotions and offers, thereby improving consumer experiences and driving sales. It also explores various system components essential for LBS functionality and evaluates their effectiveness in real-world retail scenarios. The findings suggest that LBS can significantly boost marketing strategies by providing tailored content and timely information.

Keywords: Location-Based Services (LBS), Retail Marketing, Mobile Commerce, Customer Engagement, Personalized Promotions

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INTRODUCTION

Location-based services (LBS) in marketing have become an essential tool for businesses looking to enhance customer engagement and improve targeting precision. LBS are mobile applications that provide information depending on the location of the user. To make LBS work, different system components are needed, i.e., mobile devices, positioning, communication networks, and service and content provider. LBS consume in order to provide the consumer with adapted information. Mobile commerce services that utilize information about the current location of the person using a mobile device.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Data-Driven Insights LBS provide valuable data about consumer behavior and preferences, enabling retailers to tailor marketing strategies more effectively (Fang et al., 2015).

Enhanced Shopping Experience Studies indicate that LBS can improve the shopping experience by providing relevant offers, reducing search time, and increasing convenience (Shankar et al., 2016).

Increased Engagement and Loyalty Research shows that LBS can enhance consumer engagement and loyalty by offering personalized interactions and rewards (Balaji & Roy, 2017).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To Evaluate Consumer Awareness and Adoption.
- To Analyze Consumer Behavior and Engagement.
- To Identify Challenges and Concerns.
- To Examine the Impact on Retail Marketing Effectiveness.
- To Explore Demographic and Behavioral Differences.

These objectives will help ensure that your study is comprehensive and focused, providing valuable insights into the role and impact of location-based services in retail marketing. Adjust or refine these objectives as needed to align with your specific research interests and goals.

METHODOLOGY

It has used multi-stage proportionate random sampling has used for this study. The direct personal interview method will be adopted to collect the data from sample respondents.

Table-1

Gender of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	26	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Female	34	56.7	56.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table-2

Age of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	13	21.7	21.7	21.7
	25-34	12	20.0	20.0	41.7
	35-44	12	20.0	20.0	61.7
	45-54	12	20.0	20.0	81.7
	Above 55	11	18.3	18.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table -3

Location of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Urban	38	63.3	63.3	63.3
	Rural	22	36.7	36.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 4

Income of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 25,000	10	16.7	16.7	16.7
	25,000 - 50,000	21	35.0	35.0	51.7
	50,000 - 75,000	12	20.0	20.0	71.7
	75,000 - 1,00,000	11	18.3	18.3	90.0
	Above 1,00,000	6	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 5

Are you aware of LBS used by Retailers					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	36	60.0	60.0	60.0
	No	24	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 6

Have you ever Marketing promotion from retailer based on your location					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	33	55.0	55.0	55.0
	No	27	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 7

How often do you receive location- based Offers from retailers					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Daily	8	13.3	13.3	13.3
	Weekly	15	25.0	25.0	38.3
	Monthly	23	38.3	38.3	76.7
	Rarely	11	18.3	18.3	95.0
	Never	3	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 8

How do you usually receive location – based notifications					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Mobile Apps	19	31.7	31.7	31.7
	SMS	11	18.3	18.3	50.0
	Email	5	8.3	8.3	58.3
	Social media	25	41.7	41.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table – 9

How do you feel about receiving location-based offers					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very positive	27	45.0	45.0	45.0
	Somewhat Positive	25	41.7	41.7	86.7
	Neutral	4	6.7	6.7	93.3
	Somewhat Negative	2	3.3	3.3	96.7
	Very Negative	2	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 10

Have you ever made a purchase as a result of a location- based offer					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	71.7	71.7	71.7
	No	17	28.3	28.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 11

What types of location – based offers are you most interested in					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Discounts and Coupons	4	6.7	6.7	6.7
	New product Alerts	13	21.7	21.7	28.3
	Event Invitations	9	15.0	15.0	43.3
	Loyalty rewards	28	46.7	46.7	90.0
	Others	6	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 12

How do you perceive the value of LBS in enhancing your shopping experience					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Valuable	24	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Somewhat Valuable	21	35.0	35.0	75.0
	Neutral	4	6.7	6.7	81.7
	Somewhat not Valuable	6	10.0	10.0	91.7
	Not valuable at all	5	8.3	8.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table - 13

What concerns do you have about LBS					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Privacy issues	21	35.0	35.0	35.0
	frequency of notification	24	40.0	40.0	75.0
	Relevance of offers	7	11.7	11.7	86.7
	Battery Usage	4	6.7	6.7	93.3
	Others	4	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Majority of 56.7% female respondents location-based services in retail marketing. The age group of 18-24 location-based services in retail marketing 21.7%. Income Rs25,000 – Rs.50,000 Most of the respondents (35%) location-based services in retail marketing. 60% of respondents aware of LBS used by retailers,55% of respondents marketing promotion from Retailer and 38.3% of respondents weekly receive location based offers from retailers. Social media 41.7% of respondents usually receive location based notification,45% of respondents very positive feel about receiving offers and 46.7% of respondents loyalty rewards most interested in location based offers.

FINDINGS

The findings reveal that a significant portion of consumers are aware of LBS, with a majority receiving location-based notifications and offers through mobile apps and SMS. Consumers generally perceive these notifications positively, particularly when they result in tangible benefits such as discounts and coupons. The study identifies demographics most responsive to LBS, including younger consumers in urban areas with higher income levels. Moreover, the analysis highlights consumers' preferences for specific types of offers and their willingness to engage with LBS despite concerns over privacy and notification frequency.

SUGGESTIONS

The following are the suggestions that appeared while analyzing the study.

- Marketers can target users in specific geographic areas, ensuring that promotions are relevant to their immediate environment.
- LBS provide valuable data on consumer behavior, helping business understand their audiences preferences and patterns.

CONCLUSION

LBS are a powerful tool in the modern marketing tool kit enabling business to connect with consumers in meaningful and personalized ways. As technology advances, the potential for LBS in marketing will continue to grow, offering new opportunities for innovation and customer engagement.

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